

National Plan for Music Education debate – November 2022

Birmingham Music Education Research Group, Birmingham City University

About the Birmingham Music Education Research Group

The Birmingham Music Education Research Group ([BMERG](#)) is a collective of researchers based at Birmingham City University (BCU) and Royal Birmingham Conservatoire (RBC) and is one of the leading music education research centres in the UK. Our work has been part of the evidence base upon which government draws for policy-making in music education, with our projects being noted in the new National Plan for Music Education (NPME) and previous parliamentary debates. BMERG prides itself on researching *with* the sector, representing the voices of those in practice with cutting-edge research practices to bring robust and reliable evidence and analysis into the hands of music educators, organisations, and policymakers.

For three years BMERG analysed national Music Education Hub activity data, reporting on the impacts and outcomes of the annual c. £75 million Music Education Hub grant investment. We reported on activity and analysed data that supported more than 700,000 children to access music lessons in 2018/19 for Arts Council England and the Department for Education, informing policy debates and refining future data collection processes to enhance the usefulness of data and reduce the administrative burden on Music Education Hubs (MEHs). BMERG has also brought the debate on an accessible and diverse music curriculum across UK schools into the public eye and highlighted the importance of musical learning provision for young people in Whole Class Ensemble Tuition (WCET) programmes. It is on the back of this reputation that BCU are now the lead research partners for Arts Council England's flagship 'Fair and Inclusive Music Midlands' initiative. We also have long-standing research partnerships with the One-Handed Musical Instrument (OHMI) Trust and Music Mark, further demonstrating the high regard in which our research is held.

You can find out more about our wider work, recent and ongoing projects, and the impact our research is having [here](#).

Should you wish to discuss any of these points further, would like to know more about our work, or receive details of our future events and reports, please contact adam.whittaker@bcu.ac.uk. We would welcome any conversations relating to our work and music education more generally.

Dr Adam Whittaker, Head of Pedagogy at Royal Birmingham Conservatoire writing on behalf of the Birmingham Music Education Research Group at Birmingham City University.

Our Research and the refreshed National Plan for Music Education

We have identified three key areas of the revised NPME where we feel our work has strong relevance: 1) Composing; 2) Access to opportunities and qualifications; 3) Delivery and workforce. This short briefing document provides summaries of our findings in relation to these points, along with hyperlinks to our research reports should you wish to examine this context more fully. We have also outlined key questions which we feel could facilitate deeper consideration as this new plan is enacted and mobilised.

Composing

- **Investing in composing training:** Experience of musicianship alone is not enough to facilitate young people in their composing and Music Leaders need the opportunity for their own professional development. There is likely to be a role for MEHs in this. [Go Compose report](#) (p. 18).
- **Emphasising the place of composing in music education:** Composing is a part of the National Curriculum, and is significant in music in Key Stage 4 (14-16 year olds) and Key Stage 5 (16-18 year olds) too. At present less emphasis is given to composing provision than is the case for musical performing. This would benefit from being addressed nationally in a joined-up fashion. [Go Compose report](#) (p.19).
- **Clarifying progression routes in composing:** Whilst progression routes for young performers are clearly mapped out on a local, regional, and national basis, the same is not true for composing and young composers. It would benefit from more joined-up thinking and provision. [Go Compose report](#) (p. 19).

Access to opportunities and qualifications

- **Access to qualifications:** The opportunity to study A-level music seems likely to end first for those children who are at a disadvantage, especially as we are seeing a decline in both the number of pupils being entered and the number of schools running the qualification. Given the more precarious position of Key Stage 5 (KS5) music in many disadvantaged schools and colleges, there are significant knock-on implications on the wider landscape of musical activity in these school contexts ([Whittaker & Fautley, 2021](#)).
- **Geographic discrepancies in entry levels:** proportionally, there are twice as many A-level Music students in the East of England as there are in the West Midlands. This points to significant differences in the availability of progression routes across regions ([Whittaker & Fautley, 2021](#)).
- **Key Stage 5 offerings and disadvantage attainment gaps:** a number of local authorities across the Midlands region have high A-level disadvantage attainment gaps. For example, in Coventry, where the disadvantage attainment gap is 3.3 grades, there were just 8 A-level music entries in 2020. In Staffordshire there were just 21 A-level music entries in 2020, where the A-level disadvantage attainment gap is 3.5. This means that A-level music opportunities are concentrated in high

advantage areas, meaning that disadvantaged students may encounter additional barriers to access this musical progression route ([Whittaker & Fautley, 2021](#)).

Delivery and workforce

- **Partnerships:** The refreshed NPME is predicated on the idea that partnerships can broaden the offer available to children and young people. Our work has shown that partnerships can have mixed efficacy, concluding that the notions of joining up practice in the original NPME was susceptible to flawed models underpinned by ‘victory narratives’. Before entering a partnership and joining up practices, partners need to have in-depth understandings of each other’s starting points, positionalities, and goals. It is only from that point onwards that beneficial partnerships can be co-developed ([Kinsella et al., 2022](#)).
- **Regional disparities in cultural offer:** Some areas of the country will be better serviced with a range of cultural providers and practitioners than others. Urban areas with nationally significant musical organisations can leverage a greater range of activities, or are able to do this at lower costs than rural MEHs. Allied to this is the patchiness of school engagement with MEHs, with the national average of school engagement sitting at 81% and falling to below 50% in some MEH areas.
- **Workforce preparation:** The next generation of music educators need to have access to high quality training and development opportunities. Recent work at RBC has shown the value in engaging recent conservatoire graduates as pedagogical role models for current students. Involving graduates in sharing their early-career experiences with current students and staff connects teachers and practitioners with a ‘wider music education ecology’ can help to ensure that they are ‘best equipped to support children and young people’, both of which are aspirations of the refreshed NPME ([Shaw, 2021](#)).
- It is implied within NPME2 that instrumental music teachers belong to an ‘out-of-school workforce’, furthering a divide between classroom teachers with QTS from instrumental teachers who are classed as ‘unqualified’. We suggest that is an oversight, given that alongside those instrumental teachers working in private practice, significant numbers deliver music teaching in classrooms ([Shaw, 2021](#)).

Key questions

Composing

1. Recent research has shown that composing does not receive the same attention as performing from MEHs. What specific provisions are there in the refreshed NPME to support the development of young people’s composing?
2. The NPME references ‘music technology’ 29 times, noting its importance in ‘continuing to break down barriers to equitable access to music education into the future’. The £25 million

equipment fund is certainly welcome, but how is the focus on technology to be funded given that many of the musical instruments already in circulation are in dire need of service, repair and/or replacement?

Access

1. The new National Plan is called ‘The Power of Music to change lives’, but Key Stage 5 provision is only referenced once in the entire document. Under the new NPME framework, how many children from disadvantaged backgrounds will be able to continue through to advanced stages of musical learning?
2. The NPME talks a great deal about inclusive and accessible opportunities, including for those from disadvantaged backgrounds and pupils with SEND. What provision is there in the NPME for teachers and hub staff to engage with high-quality training and current research in the field, given that many are already working at full capacity on limited contracts?
3. The NPME notes ‘space for rehearsals and individual practice’ (p. 19) as a key feature of high-quality school music provision. If a school does not have these, what steps can they take to ensure that they can deliver the high-quality music provision set out in the plan?

Delivery

1. The new National Plan is predicated on partnership working as a key delivery model. What mechanisms are in place to ensure that access is both equal and equitable across different regions with varying rural/urban densities? It should not be the case that young musicians in some areas will receive a less varied offer simply by virtue of where they live.
2. What safeguards are in place that partnership working does not further contribute to the growth of ‘outsourced’ models of curriculum and MEH delivery of core roles?
3. As partnership working becomes an ever-more important aspect of music education delivery, what safeguards are in place to protect against even greater fragmentation with MEHs operating over much greater geographical areas, accountable to a much broader constituency?
4. There is a clear aspiration towards a more diverse workforce. In what ways does the NPME enable a more diverse range of young musicians to reach advanced levels of learning and become the next generation of music educators?
5. To help connect current students and staff teachers/practitioners with a wider music education environment to best support young musicians, what key performance indicators/expectations will be given to the new Centre of Excellence for CPD?
6. Given that many instrumental teachers, who are perceived as ‘unqualified’, are delivering music teaching in many classrooms, is there scope to use the pilot of a new Portable Flexi-Job Apprenticeship to offer training for instrumental teachers emerging from HEMIs? Might the delivery of the NPME be enhanced by new NPQs to support instrumental music teachers?